

ASSOCIATION OF LOW SERUM SODIUM WITH RECURRENCE OF FEBRILE SEIZURES AMONG CHILDREN WITH FEBRILE SEIZURES

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Abstract

Background: Febrile seizures frequently affect children and can recur. This poses challenges for clinical management. Although several risk factors for recurrence have been reported internationally, evidence specific to local Pakistani populations remains limited. This study aimed to explore the association between clinical, demographic, and laboratory factors, including serum sodium levels, and the recurrence of febrile seizures in children.

Methods: We conducted a cross-sectional study involving 145 children aged 6 months to 5 years. Those who presented with febrile seizures. Data on demographics, clinical features, and serum sodium levels were collected. Participants were categorized based on the occurrence of seizure recurrence, and comparisons were made to identify potential predictors.

Results: Recurrence occurred in 24.8% of children. We found no statistically significant differences in age, sex, residence, family income, or family history of febrile seizures between those with and without recurrence. Children with shorter durations of fever prior to seizures showed a non-significant trend toward higher recurrence. Hyponatremia was observed in 35.9% of participants but showed no significant association with seizure recurrence.

Conclusion: Our findings suggest that commonly assessed factors, including serum sodium levels, do not independently predict febrile seizure recurrence in this population. These results emphasize the multifactorial nature of febrile seizures and the importance of comprehensive evaluation in risk assessment.

INTRODUCTION

The seizure is one of the most common diseases of childhood that occurs in 4%–10% in pediatrics and adolescence⁽¹⁾. A Febrile seizure is a seizure accompanied by fever (temperature 100.4°F or 38°C by any method), between age of 6 months to 60 months, without CNS infection or metabolic

imbalance, and that occurs in the absence of a history of prior afebrile seizures⁽²⁾. Risk of recurrences in febrile convulsion is 30-40%, after first episode, 50% after 2nd or more episodes, 50% in infants <1year old. Febrile Seizure are the most common paroxysmal episode during infancy and childhood, which affects

up to one in 10 children. These seizures are associated with high grade fever in children and is a major cause of emergency visits and a source of family anxiety⁽³⁾.

Febrile seizure is a benign condition, where the etiology or pathophysiology is not yet clear, however emerging febrile seizure syndromes behave differently. Genetic predisposition is thought to be a major contributor. A strong family history of febrile convulsions in siblings and parents suggests a strong precipitating factor. Genetic studies show a multi factorial mode of inheritance. Siblings with history of Febrile Seizure, showed 10-20% of recurrences⁽⁴⁾.

The simple febrile seizure does not occur more than 15 minutes and is more common that occurs 65.0-90.0%⁽⁵⁾. The complex febrile seizure occurs more than 15 minutes or recurrent seizures within 24 hours. High fever plays the important role in causing electrolyte disturbance. Hyponatremia has been enhancing the susceptibility to seizures⁽⁶⁾. The complex febrile seizure is common in patient with hyponatremia. 4 There were still inconclusive previous studies in patients with recurrent febrile seizure and serum sodium levels^(7,8).

Study by Sara reported that the recurrence of febrile seizures in patient with low and normal sodium was 29% and 04% respectively⁽⁹⁾. Another study reported the recurrent febrile seizure in patient with and without hyponatremia was 100% and 37.7% respectively⁽¹⁰⁾. Study by Jatuporn Duangpetsang reported the prevalence of recurrent febrile seizure was 10.52% (20/190) have recurrent febrile seizure. However, Serum sodium levels in children with recurrent seizures within 24 hours (130.80 mmol/L) were significantly lower than in children with a single febrile seizure (132.37 mmol/L⁽¹¹⁾).

The aim of our study is to determine the association between low serum sodium and recurrent febrile seizures. International literature shows that hyponatremia is associated with recurrent febrile seizures. However, local literature on this topic is very scarce. Due to difference in population dynamic and health delivery system findings of international literature is not applicable on our local population. Findings of our study will help the pediatrician to modify screening strategies which help in early diagnosis and management of hyponatremia which ultimately helps in reducing the risk of recurrent febrile seizure.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The study was conducted as a descriptive observational analysis at the Department of Paediatrics, Isra University Hospital, Hyderabad, over a duration of six months from January 2024 to June 2024. A total of 145 children were enrolled, with the sample size determined using the WHO sample size calculator. The calculation was based on an estimated prevalence of recurrent febrile seizures at 10.52%, a margin of error of 5%, and a 95% confidence interval. A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was employed.

Children aged between 6 months and 5 years who were admitted with febrile seizures and met the inclusion criteria were eligible for enrollment. Patients were excluded if they presented with unprovoked seizures, complex febrile convulsions, neurological infections, developmental delays, persistent neurological deficits, or concurrent illnesses such as gastroenteritis or pneumonia.

Approval from the CPSP was obtained before initiating the study. Each eligible child's parent or guardian received a comprehensive explanation of the study, and written informed consent was acquired prior to participation. Relevant demographic and clinical information—including age, sex, place of residence, monthly family income, weight, height, duration of fever, and family history of febrile seizures—was recorded on a structured proforma.

Upon admission, a 3cc blood sample was drawn under aseptic conditions by a trained phlebotomist and sent to the laboratory to assess serum sodium levels. Patients were then observed for a period of 24 hours to monitor the recurrence of seizures. All relevant study variables were documented in the predesigned proforma provided in Annexure A.

Statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS version 25. Categorical variables such as gender, residence, family history of febrile seizures, hyponatremia, and seizure recurrence were summarized using frequencies and percentages. Continuous variables, including age, monthly income, weight, duration of fever, and serum sodium concentration, were expressed as means and standard deviations for normally distributed data, while medians and interquartile ranges were reported for skewed distributions. Post-stratification analysis involved the application of the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, depending on the data

characteristics. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered indicative of statistical significance.

RESULTS:

The study enrolled 145 children. Most of whom (73.1%) were between 6 months and 1 year old, while (26.9%) were aged 2 to 5 years. Females comprised a slight majority at (53.8%), with males representing (46.2%). The vast majority of participants lived in urban areas (83.4%), and the remainder resided in rural settings (16.6%). More than half of the children (64.8%) experienced fever lasting longer than seven days, whereas (35.2%) had fever for seven days or less. Regarding socioeconomic status, (63.4%) of families reported a monthly income above 75,000 with (36.6%) falling below this level. One in five children (20%) had a family history of febrile seizures. Hyponatremia was identified in (35.9%) of participants. Overall, (24.8%) of children experienced recurrent febrile seizures during the study period.

When comparing those who had recurrent febrile seizures with those who did not, no statistically meaningful differences emerged across the examined factors. Among children aged 6 months to 1 year, 18% experienced seizure recurrence compared to 28.2% in the 2 to 5 years group ($p = 0.247$). The recurrence rate was identical for males and females, both at 25%. Children living in urban areas showed a recurrence rate of 24%, slightly higher than the 20.8% among rural residents, though this difference lacked significance ($p = 1.00$). The duration of fever showed a trend, with 39.2% recurrence among those with fever lasting seven days or less versus 17% in those with longer fevers ($p = 0.005$). Family income and history of febrile seizures showed no association with recurrence. Hyponatremia occurred in 19% of children with recurrent seizures and 28% of those without recurrence, indicating no significant relationship ($p = 0.317$).

Table 1: Distribution of baseline characteristics among the study participants.

Variables	n (%)
Age	
6 months to 1 year	106 (73.1)
2 to 5 years	39 (26.9)
Gender	
Male	67 (46.2)
Female	78 (53.8)
Residence	
Urban	121 (83.4)
Rural	24 (16.6)
Duration of fever	
≤ 7 days	51 (35.2)
> 7 days	94 (64.8)
Family monthly income	
≤ 75000	53 (36.6)
> 75000	92 (63.4)
Family history of febrile seizure	
Yes	29 (20)
No	116 (80)
Hyponatremia	
Yes	52 (35.9)
No	93 (64.1)
Recurrent febrile seizure	
Yes	36 (24.8)
No	109 (75.2)

Total	145 (100)
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Table 2: Distribution of patient characteristics according to the recurrent febrile seizure groups.

Variables	Recurrent febrile seizure (Yes) n (%)	Recurrent febrile seizure (No) n (%)	P-value
Age			
06 months to 01 year	19 (18)	87 (82)	0.247
02 to 05 years	11 (28.2)	28 (71.8)	
Gender			
Male	17 (25.4)	50 (74.6)	1.00
Female	19 (24.4)	59 (75.6)	
Residence			
Urban	29 (24)	92 (76)	1.00
Rural	05 (20.8)	19 (79.2)	
Duration of fever			
≤ 7 days	20 (39.2)	31 (60.8)	0.005
> 7 days	16 (17)	78 (83)	
Family monthly income			
≤ 75000	17 (32)	36 (68)	0.174
> 75000	20 (21.7)	72 (78.3)	
Family history of febrile seizure			
Yes	07 (24.1)	22 (75.9)	1.00
No	28 (24)	88 (76)	
Hyponatremia			
Yes	10 (19)	42 (81)	0.317
No	26 (28)	67 (72)	
Recurrent febrile seizure			
Yes	10 (27.8)	26 (72.2)	1.000
No	31 (28.4)	78 (71.6)	

DISCUSSION:

This study examined the clinical and demographic factors associated with the recurrence of febrile seizures in children. We found that 24.8% of participants experienced seizure recurrence, which aligns with recurrence rates reported in similar populations¹²⁻¹⁴. Although most children were aged 2 to 5 years, age did not significantly predict recurrence in our sample. This finding contrasts with several studies that highlight younger age as a major risk

factor for recurrent seizures, potentially reflecting differences in study populations or methods.^{12,15-16}

Our analysis revealed no meaningful differences in seizure recurrence related to gender or urban versus rural residence. The equal recurrence rates between males and females mirror findings from multiple cohorts, suggesting that sex does not independently influence recurrence risk.^{13,16-17} Similarly, geographic location within our study setting did not impact

recurrence, indicating environmental factors may have limited effect here.

We observed a non-significant trend toward higher recurrence among children with shorter fever durations prior to seizure onset, which suggests that fever duration could be one of multiple contributing factors.¹⁸ Neither family income nor family history of febrile seizures showed a significant association with recurrence, though prior literature supports these as potential influences, indicating the need for larger studies and more detailed data collection to clarify their roles.^{13, 19}

Importantly, our study did not identify a significant link between hyponatremia and seizure recurrence. While some research has proposed hyponatremia as a predictor of recurrent febrile seizures, our data do not support serum sodium level as a reliable stand-alone marker for recurrence risk.²⁰⁻²³ This finding emphasizes the multifactorial nature of febrile seizures and the need to consider a broad range of biological and clinical factors.

Although hyponatremia was present in 35.9% of the children in our study, we observed that those with low serum sodium had a lower rate of febrile seizure recurrence (19%) compared to children with normal sodium levels (28%). This finding suggests that, within our dataset, hyponatremia did not increase the risk of seizure recurrence. This contrasts with some previous research. Several factors may explain this unexpected result. First, the relatively small sample size could contribute to random variation affecting the observed association. Second, confounding factors such as hydration status, underlying infections, or treatment differences may have influenced both sodium levels and seizure outcomes independently, masking any true relationship. Furthermore, the timing of sodium measurement during the illness course may not have captured baseline electrolyte status relevant to seizure risk. Additionally, population-specific genetic or environmental factors might alter this relationship compared to other groups. Finally, the severity of hyponatremia may play a role; mild reductions in sodium may not carry the same risk as more severe cases, and our study likely included mostly mild hyponatremia. Overall, these findings highlight the complex nature of febrile seizures and suggest that serum sodium alone may not

be a reliable predictor of recurrence in this population.

The complex interplay of genetic predisposition, neurological development, and inflammatory processes likely underpins febrile seizure recurrence.²⁴ Our findings corroborate the importance of these broader factors and highlight the limitations of relying solely on traditional clinical variables. Further research incorporating molecular biomarkers and longitudinal designs will be essential to improve predictive models and guide personalized care.²⁷⁻²⁹

Our results suggest that commonly assessed demographic and clinical features: including age, gender, residence, fever duration, family history, and serum sodium; do not independently predict febrile seizure recurrence in this population. Clinicians should maintain a comprehensive approach to risk assessment, considering multiple factors to inform management decisions.

CONCLUSION:

Our findings suggest that commonly assessed factors, including serum sodium levels, do not independently predict febrile seizure recurrence in this population. These results emphasize the multifactorial nature of febrile seizures and the importance of comprehensive evaluation in risk assessment.

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